

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

SEASONAL ACTIVITY OF “TIGER” STRIPES ON SATURN’S MOON ENCELADUS

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Abstract

The significant inclination of the plane of the satellite’s equator to the plane of the orbit of the central planet allows us to record differences in the flow of solar energy to different latitudinal zones during their rotation around the Sun. The equator of Enceladus, like Saturn itself, is inclined to the plane of the planet’s orbit by almost 27° . With a significant eccentricity of the planet’s orbit (0.06), Enceladus and Saturn pass the perihelion of the orbit at a distance of ≈ 9 AU in summer in the southern hemisphere, and aphelion – at a distance of more than 10 AU during the summer season in the northern hemisphere. This leads to the fact that the southern hemisphere of Saturn and Enceladus receive on average a quarter more energy from the Sun than the northern. Such conditions affect on the influx of sunlight to the latitudinal zones and changes in physical characteristics on the surface of the satellite and in the atmosphere of the planet. The images obtained by “Cassini” devices show that almost the entire polar region is covered with fresh ice, shows geyser emissions, the presence of “tiger” stripes up to 130 km long, up to 2 km thick and up to 0.5 km deep. It is through them that water is released into the surrounding space from the ocean below the surface of the satellite. Spectral data obtained by “Cassini” equipment also indicated an abnormally high flow of heat through these bands, which are the source of water geysers. Our analysis showed that in 2022, Enceladus is moving from the polar day in the northern hemisphere, and is approaching the equinox in 2024-2025, and later – to the summer season in satellite southern hemisphere. And this should cause a significant increase in geyser activity in the polar region. Therefore, it will be useful to observe the seasonal increase in geyser activity in the “tiger” stripes around the satellite’s south pole, and to dedicate to this fact a special program of observations using infrared equipment on Keck telescopes, Very Large Telescope and space telescopes.

Keywords: Enceladus, seasonal changes, geyser activity, water ocean, ice surface, tiger stripes.

Features of solar irradiation of planets and their satellites. For the planets Venus, Earth, Mars, Saturn, Uranus and Neptune, there is a significant tilt between the planes of their equators and orbits. Therefore, during the rotation of these planets around the Sun, we register significant differences in the arrival of solar energy to their different latitude zones. For example, the equator of the planet Saturn is significantly inclined to the plane of its orbit. We have been studying the changing seasons in its atmosphere since 1977. In works [20, 22, 26, 27, 30] we registered significant changes in the visible atmosphere of Saturn. We explained them as seasonal variations in incoming solar energy. For our analysis, we used the results of numerous observational data at the equinoxes in 1966, 1980, 1995 and 2010. Our calculations [24] showed that the

southern hemisphere of Saturn, on average, receives a quarter more energy from the Sun than the northern one.

The period of rotation of the planet around the Sun is 29.45 years. Saturn’s orbit has a significant eccentricity (0.06). Moreover, the planet passes the perihelion of its orbit at a distance of about 9 AU in the epoch of summer in the southern hemisphere, and aphelion – at a distance of more than 10 AU during the summer in the northern hemisphere (Fig. 1). For this reason, the southern hemisphere receives 25% more energy from the Sun than the northern hemisphere. This happens because the equatorial plane of the planet is inclined to the plane of its orbit by an angle of almost 27° . And at the equinoxes, Saturn is at an average distance from the Sun.

Fig. 1. The dependence of the change in the radius-vector (Δ) of Saturn upon changes in the Saturnicentric inclination (φ) in 1966-2025 [29].

Especially noticeable changes in the supply of solar energy are observed at high latitudes of the planet. After all, at the maximum angles of inclination, they can exceed the energy input by orders of magnitude if the rings of Saturn are visible from the edge (Fig. 2) [29].

Fig. 2. The arrival of solar energy to different latitudes (φ) of Saturn depending on the saturnocentric inclination B [29].

To conduct this research, we used the results of our photometric and spectral observations [8, 22-26, 30], the results of observations by many amateurs and other scientists [6, 14, 21] and data from space vehicles

and space telescopes [12], received in the period from 1964 to 2020. During this time, there were four consecutive passages of the plane of the rings of the planet through the plane of the Earth's orbit at the equinoxes.

They were repeated on Saturn every ≈ 14.7 years: in 1966, 1980, 1995 and in 2010, when Saturn was at the average distance to the Sun, and both hemispheres were irradiated by it equally (Fig. 1). And since Enceladus (as well as most of Saturn's satellites) moves practically in the equatorial plane of the planet (inclination less than 0.02°), when the libration is less than 1.5° , it is almost equally indicated on the physical characteristics of the upper atmosphere of the planet and the surface of the satellite.

The subsurface sea in the southern polar region. In the period from 2004 to 2017, "Cassini" made almost one and a half hundred approaches, making more than 2 dozen fairly close flybys of Enceladus. Its entire surface was covered with ice. It was using the data collected during the operation of the apparatus that a global infrared map of this satellite was created. On

Fig. 3 shows five different views of Enceladus' surface. The three images in the top row show the front, trailing, and Saturn-facing hemispheres of the satellite; the two in the bottom row show the northern and southern polar regions. The colors indicate differences in the properties of the ice on the surface: red - corresponds to fresh and smooth ice, blue - to older ice. This map shows that the polar region around the South Pole is covered with a lot of very fresh ice. Its presence is well explained by geysers, which actively eject water into the surrounding space from the ocean beneath the surface of Enceladus. Four faults of "tiger" stripes, 130 km long, are clearly visible there. And in this place, not a single impact crater was found near the bands. This indicates the geological youth of these formations. That is, the origin of the bands is related to the processes in the bowels of the satellite.

Fig. 3. Maps of different hemispheres of Enceladus (https://universemagazine.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/A_new_view_of_Enceladus_annotated_pillars.jpg).

The south polar region of Enceladus attracted attention due to the presence of a thermal anomaly inside it [17] and the ejection of water geysers through cracks in its surface [4, 13, 16, 35]. Observational data showed the presence of a thin icy lithosphere there and the possible presence of liquid quite close to the surface. This does not coincide with the point of view proposed in [13], that the shape of Enceladus most closely corresponds to a body that has not passed the stage of internal differentiation. An alternative explanation for the shape of Enceladus is proposed in [2], in which there is local heating in the southern polar region, which leads to the melting of ice at a certain depth under the crust and the formation of an internal polar sea. Density estimates (1.609 g/cm^3) indicate that it is almost entirely water ice, with significant percentages of silicates and

iron. Therefore, it is believed that its interior can be significantly heated due to the decay of radioactive elements. To maintain the observed geological activity, the core of Enceladus must be partially molten. Helping to maintain such a high temperature of some areas in the interior of the satellite can also provide tidal heating. It should be the main source of existing geological activity.

If the interior of Enceladus were heated only by internal radiogenic heat sources, its energy output would be up to 300 MW [5]. However, the estimated heat balance shows that such amount of it would clearly not be enough to support melting in a thick icy substance without involving ideas about the ice of an unusual composition and about the additional insulation of this layer. To obtain an estimate of a reasonable thick-

ness (50-100 km) of the water ice shell under the radiogenic scenario, changes in the core temperature would barely reach 10-30 K above the surface temperature of 70-75 K. Additional internal energy is required to further heat the polar sea below the surface, can be obtained from the tidal mechanism due to changes in the eccentricity of the orbit as a result of resonant interaction with another satellite of Saturn – Dione [3, 17, 18].

The presence of propane and acetylene found in the southern polar geysers during spectral observations may indicate that water on Enceladus is in contact with the hot silicate layer of the core [9]. That is, in fact, the warming and melting of the ice sheet is quite deep. In [13], the shape of Enceladus is represented by an ellipsoid with an axis directed to Saturn of 256.6 ± 0.5 km, directed along the orbit of 251.4 ± 0.2 km, and a polar

axis of 248.3 ± 0.2 km. The observed deviation from the ellipsoid at the south pole with a larger radius of curvature can be interpreted as evidence of a peculiar bending of the surface in the southern polar region due to the formation of the internal polar sea there (Fig. 4), and the ejection of a significant amount of water from it through geysers. The possible reason for the presence of a thermal anomaly and geysers at the south pole of Enceladus is indicated in the article [10]. There is a scenario for the periodic reorientation of Enceladus' rotation axis due to the differentiation of molten rocky material of low density and warm ice in the middle of the satellite. A similar process can lead to a change in the rotational moment of the satellite. You can try to register it with the help of a gravimeter during the next close flybys of spacecraft near Enceladus.

Fig. 4. Model of the internal structure of Enceladus with the south polar depression from heating, melting and geyser eruptions [2].

To explain the increase in temperature and the appearance of geyser activity there, such hypotheses were proposed as the release of heat from a subsurface reservoir of liquid water at a temperature of up to 273 K [13, 15], sublimation of ice on the outer surface at a temperature above 180 K [17], decompression and dissociation of clathrates [7] at a temperature in the crevices of about 140 K, and in the course of heating directed to the surface of the satellite [11]. Elevated temperatures in the vents of geyser emissions should heat nearby areas on the surface. Such processes may explain some of the thermal effects observed with "Cassini".

The maps of the southern polar region obtained by the "Cassini" apparatus [1, 17] also confirmed the localization of heated material along the "tiger" stripes (Fig. 3). The results presented in [1] showed that the heating in the "tiger" stripes occurs precisely through these faults, and then through the holes on the outer surface, a liquid is released from the sea, which can be the direct cause of the observed thermal emission.

Change in the activity of the hemispheres of Saturn's satellite. So, the results of research on Enceladus showed that linear features in the southern polar region of the satellite, called "tiger" stripes, have abnormally high heat sources and are the obvious source of geysers observed in 2004-2011. Infrared maps of Enceladus showed their alignment with geological activity around the south pole. Moreover, similar features in infrared rays are visible in the front hemisphere already near the northern polar region of the satellite. This indicates that there are places covered with fresh ice. And

therefore, similar geological processes occur in both hemispheres of this satellite of Saturn. The appearance of fresh ice in the Northern Hemisphere can be associated either with the same currents as in the Southern Hemisphere, or with the gradual percolation of material from the subglacial ocean to the surface.

The ocean under the ice crust of the surface is in a liquid aggregate state, possibly due to tidal forces. According to the samples obtained in 2014, taken by the Cassini apparatus in emissions from the surface of the planet during a close flyby, it was possible to obtain some conclusions about the composition of this water. Emissions consisted of almost 93% H₂O, up to 4% nitrogen, up to 3% CO₂, up to 1% methane and traces of ammonia, acetylene, propane, etc. These data may even indicate the presence of microbial forms of extraterrestrial life on the satellite. Water reservoirs on Saturn's moon are up to 30 km deep and can cover its entire surface. If the shallowest layers of water in the Earth's ocean are on the surface, then on Enceladus the deeper the water, the warmer the water becomes. Studies point to the possibility of the existence of oceanic currents in the ocean of Enceladus, as well as in the Earth's. Their existence is indicated by the study of the icy surface of the satellite. So, it turned out that the ice layer is quite uneven, and near the poles it is much thinner than at the equator. It is clear that the thin areas are the result of melting, and the thicker ones are the result of freezing.

We believe that the reason that the ice crust near the poles is thinner is the presence of seasonal changes in the heating of the polar regions during the rotation of

Enceladus together with the central planet around the Sun. We will remind that the long polar day for the southern polar circle takes place at distances of about 9 AU. And for the northern polar circle, the polar day occurs by more than 1 AU further - at a distance of more than 10 AU. This excess heat of more than 25% in the southern polar circle may prove to be quite enough for the conditions in the southern polar regions to allow the formation of much more powerful geyser emissions than is the case in the northern polar regions of the satellite. Not only that, but such excess thermal energy also leads to the formation of the well-known four "tiger" stripes – faults up to 130 km long, up to 2 km wide and up to 0.5 km deep. It is believed that the thickness of the crust near the south pole can be only about 2 km. While near the North Pole, the thickness can be up to 10 km. At middle and near-equatorial latitudes, the thickness is even greater.

Comparison of data from Fig. 3 and from the change in the radius-vector (Δ) of Saturn (Fig. 1) shows that in 2015-2017 we moved to the polar day already beyond the Arctic Circle. And although the distance from the Sun has increased by almost 0.9 a. o., and yet the maps in Fig. 3 show new formations of fresh ice (reddish shade) on the front summer hemisphere of the satellite, most likely as a result of local geyser eruptions. We now have a moment when in 2022 Enceladus, like Saturn, is leaving the polar day in the northern hemisphere, and we are approaching the equinox in 2024-2025 [34]. After that, there will be a gradual transition to the summer season in the southern hemisphere of Enceladus. And this, in turn, will cause a significant increase in geyser activity in the southern polar region.

Therefore, it would be very interesting to follow the gradual growth of geyser activity in the "tiger" stripes around the south pole of Enceladus. This fact of seasonal growth of geyser activity beyond the southern polar circle of Enceladus could be devoted to a special program of observations with the help of infrared equipment on Keck Telescopes, the Very Large Telescope and on space telescopes.

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